

PIEZOELECTRIC ENERGY HARVESTING FOR LEADLESS PACEMAKERS: THE INVESTIGATION OF PATIENTS' ECGs

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Abstract. This paper investigates the performance of a novel heart piezoelectric energy harvester. Heart-simulating experiments were based on the electrocardiogram (ECG) signals from different patients. The shape of the ECG signal as the heart motion simulation was investigated for the energy harvester performance. Amplitude-normalized ECG signals of five patients were used as input for a vibration shaker while the electrical performance was recorded. The output results, voltage, the number of energy pulses generated, and the width of the generated energy pulses were calculated. Results showed that this novel energy harvester developed 11.40 ± 0.85 V voltage, 26.4 pulses of energy in each heartbeat, and an average pulse width of 0.11 ± 0.03 ms. The results showed that the output performance of different patients is still influential. The study contributes to broadly testing piezoelectric energy harvesters for leadless pacemakers.

Keywords: Piezoelectric, Energy Harvesting, Heart, Leadless Pacemakers, ECG.

1 INTRODUCTION

Self-powered biomedical devices have the potential to revolutionise the field of medicine. The development of miniaturised, self-sustained devices would be a significant achievement, as conventional batteries are bulky, mechanically rigid, and require frequent replacements with complicated procedures or surgery. By eliminating the need for replacement surgeries due to battery depletion, self-powered implants would be more robust and multifunctional for intracardiac implants. Intracardiac leadless pacemakers (ICLP) have emerged as an alternative, reducing some of the risks of complications associated with their predecessors [1]–[3]. However, they also have a limited battery life [4]–[6], which can cause significant issues. Powering pacemakers using heartbeats has drawn some attention previously. A zigzag structure was proposed [7]; however, the dimensions are too large for intracardiac implantation. A cantilevered beam was also proposed for leadless pacemakers [8], but due to the limited length and the low frequency of heartbeats, this design faces significant challenges.

Despite the unsatisfactory power generation of current state-of-the-art energy harvesting concepts, designing, and fabricating novel self-powering ICLPs is vital for cardiovascular treatment. Such a development would significantly impact millions of patients worldwide, reducing the risks of revision surgery-related infections and device endocarditis.

Piezoelectric materials generate an electric potential when mechanically deformed. Since the human body constantly produces enormous amounts of kinetic energy, harvesting this energy through piezoelectricity could revolutionise the medical field. For instance, the heart's 1 W mechanical power [9] can power a leadless pacemaker. Piezoelectric energy harvesting can be achieved by connecting the body's mechanical motion to the piezoelectric material through periodic movements such as blood flow [10], tissue contraction [11], and cardiac/lung motions [12], [13]. However, the practical purpose of piezoelectric energy harvesting is mainly restrained by low energy output performance [14]. The body's kinetic motion is low-frequency [15]–[18], which poses significant challenges to energy conversion efficiency. Therefore, a kinetic body energy harvesting mechanism with substantial efficiency improvement is needed.

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This work further investigates a new approach to harvesting body energy inspired by the patent authors have published [19]. The presented novel energy harvester has been reported as a contact-based multi-directional energy generator with a specific design for heart energy harvesting [19]. The understudy energy harvester is robust and can generate sufficient power for the heart's pacing. However, this energy harvester needs extensive validation through experimental tests, long-term tests, and various heart motions from different patients. This study presents a collection of patients' heart motions and studies the piezoelectric energy harvester (PEH) performance under these patients' motions. Piezoelectric outputs are compared at different heart signals by statistical analysis. This study contributes to the validation of a new energy harvester for leadless pacemakers. The developed energy harvester is novel for leadless pacemakers; therefore, this study will pave the way for the application of a new practical energy harvester.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section presents the information about the leadless pacemaker, dimensions and operational information as well as the experimental setup of the novel energy harvester [20].

2.1 Leadless pacemaker piezoelectric energy harvesting

The MicraTM (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN, USA) is a leadless pacemaker, see Figure 1a, with approximately 50% volume occupied by the battery. The leadless pacemaker MicraTM uses 1.3-2.1 μA and 1.5-2.5 V typically, about 6 μW power [21].

The energy harvester comprises two piezoelectric cubes with an inner moving ball to create the contact force in heartbeat motion; see Figure 1b. The performance of this energy harvester in pig model and laboratory heart simulation has been demonstrated [20]. More detailed information about the energy harvester can be found in [20]. The volume of the energy harvester is set to be within the range of MicraTM's battery. The self-powering leadless pacemaker idea is to replace the MicraTM's battery with this energy harvester with a smaller rechargeable battery. The built sample has an AC-to-DC converter since the piezoelectric outputs are AC voltage.

Figure 1: (a) Micra™ (Medtronic, Minneapolis, MN, USA), (b) the proposed energy harvester, which can be embedded in a leadless pacemaker, and (c) an experimental setup for simulating heart motion.

2.2 Experimental heart simulation vibration

Figure 1c shows the experimental setup for the test. A vibration shaker (LDS V201 from Bruel and Kjaer, Virum, Denmark) simulated the kinetic heart motion on the leadless pacemaker PEH. The heart motion was simulated using an (electrocardiogram) ECG heart signal generated by a signal generator, which controlled a compatible amplifier (LPA 100 from Bruel and Kjaer, Virum, Denmark) to power the shaker. The input heart signal had a controlled amplitude.

The kinetic motion shape and amplitude of the human heart provide valuable data for evaluating energy harvester performance. However, obtaining precise data on the heart's motion type and amplitude is challenging. The heart is a complex organ with both electrical and mechanical indices. The ECG, a standard diagnostic tool, measures the electrical activity of the heart. The mechanical kinetic motion of the heart, which refers to the movement of the heart muscles, can provide valuable information about heart function. Electrical and dynamic heart motions exhibit similarities and characteristics that contribute to a comprehensive analysis of heart activities. While ECG signals are well-documented in the literature, the database for heart dynamic motion is limited.

ECG open datasets are widely [22]–[24] ECG signals from five normal-sinus-rhythm patients were obtained from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia database [23], [24]. Table 1 presents the patients' information and the code to refer to them. The ECG signals have heart rates and different amplitudes, see Figure 2. Each ECG has different segments. Each signal was normalized to its maximum value to obtain the unbiased ECG signals. Figure 2b shows the normalized ECG signals in a 10-second window. The heart rate and heart motion shape are uncontrolled and original from the patients' recordings. Nevertheless, the similarity of all ECG signals is the shock pattern in the ECG signal, demonstrating the sudden motion of the heart in a short period.

The heart acceleration was previously measured in an animal pig model by the authors [25]. These acceleration signals were used to set the amplitude of the ECG signal, ensuring that a comparable acceleration is

applied to the energy harvester. The ECG signals in Figure 2b were fed into the shaker with a controlled amplitude, resulting in a maximum shaker acceleration of approximately 3.5 m/s^2 , similar to [15]. The piezoelectric voltage was then measured over a long period, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Patient information [23], [24]

Patient's code	Gender	Age	Heart Rate ^a (bpm)	Number of ECG parts	Voltage recording time
100	Male	69	79	8	24 minutes
103	Male	NA	141	5	15 minutes
116	Male	68	78	8	24 minutes
209	Male	62	95	9	27 minutes
213	Male	61	111	12	36 minutes

^a Calculated from the Fast Fourier Transform of the ECG signal.

Figure 2: The ECG signals of five patients, (a) the original signals and (b) normalized amplitude signals in a 10-second window

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 3 shows the open-circuit voltage from the excitation signal of patient #100, along with a zoomed-in view. For simplicity, the voltage output is shown in Figure 3 from the four first four segments of the ECG segments. The zoomed-in view highlights the multiple energy pulses generated in each heartbeat. The plot displays four distinct signal parts with varying voltage amplitudes over time. The peak open-circuit voltage amplitude ranges between 10-12 V. The zoomed-in view reveals multiple power pulse generations.

Figure 3: The piezoelectric voltage output from excitation signals of patient #100 and the zoomed-in view of the voltage.

Furthermore, Figure 4 shows the voltage output for the patients #103, #116, #209, and #213. The plot limits of the recorded voltage plot in Figure 3 and Figure 4 were reduced for the demonstration easiness. Comparing the voltage output from these five patients' output voltage, there were scatters in the voltage output peak between different patients. These scatters also could be found within different segments of one patient ECG. Nonetheless, the scatter was not substantial.

Figure 4: The piezoelectric voltage outputs from patients #103, #116, #209, and #213 excitation signals.

Due to pulse power generation, the average of peak voltages is also reported. The average peak voltage generated for different patients is plotted in Figure 5. The voltage of each patient during the ECG segments shows discrepancies. The energy generation from the patient can be time-variable. The statistical analysis for each patient indicates a 5.0% to 14.6% variation in voltage peaks. As the average voltage for the five patients,

the voltage output average is 11.4 V, and the scatter is 7.5% of the average value.

Figure 5: The maximum piezoelectric voltage results for the five studied ECGs are (a) the pulse maximum voltage at different ECG segments, (b) the peak voltages among patients, and (c) the overall peak voltage for all patients.

The number of energy pulses for each patient is individually shown in Figure 6. On average, each heartbeat led to the generation of approximately 26 pulses. The variation in the number of pulses is 18.6%, higher than the voltage peak values. The number of pulses is more affected by the randomness of the contact force. Therefore, it is expected that the number of pulses varies more substantially. The minimum number of pulses was eight for patient #213.

The pulse width of energy pulses is another critical parameter studied for different patients' ECG signals. See Figure 7. The average pulse width is 0.10 ms for the most vital generated pulse in each heartbeat, with a variation of 33.3%. The different patients substantially affect the pulse width but have a minimum pulse width of 0.07 ms.

Figure 6: The number of piezoelectric energy pulses in each heartbeat for the five studied ECGs, (a) the pulse numbers at different ECG segments, (b) the pulse numbers among patients, and (c) the overall pulse numbers for all patients.

Figure 7: The piezoelectric energy pulse width for the five studied ECGs, (a) the energy pulse width at different ECG segments, (b) the energy pulse width among patients, and (c) the overall energy pulse width for all patients.

The previously reported values were open-circuit voltages. A resistive load test is carried out to estimate the power. Figure 8 shows the electrical performance of the energy harvester in one heartbeat. The voltage and current are separately measured. Power is the product of voltage and current. Multiple pulses of energy are

produced in one heartbeat during 0.1 seconds, as seen in **Figure 8**. The power output has ten distinct pulses, with a maximum of $389 \mu\text{W}$. This power output is considerably higher than the $6 \mu\text{W}$ requirement for Micra™.

Figure 8: The piezoelectric energy harvester's voltage, current, and power output with a resistance load connection ($8.3 \text{ k}\Omega$).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the energy generation performance of the heart's kinetic motion for the self-powering of leadless pacemakers. The investigated prospects included the kinetic motion simulation of five patients from ECG signals. The authors recently published a patent on high-efficiency piezoelectric harvesters, demonstrating excellent performance. The performance of this energy harvester has been investigated using different shapes of ECG signals from patients. While variations in output performance were inevitable due to the time-variable nature of heart kinetic motion and randomness, the generated energy from the heart's kinetic motion was satisfactory. For these five patients, over 10 V of voltage, 24 pulses of energy, and a pulse width of 0.1 ms were estimated. Our team is exploring a more comprehensive range of testing and exciting aspects of this innovative idea in self-powering medical devices.

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